

Problematizing the Issue of Open Defecation in the film Toilet- Ek Prem Katha

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Abstract:

The issue of open defecation is one of the persistent and entrenched issues in several parts of the country. Adequate sanitation is a basic human right. The lack of adequate sanitation exacerbates social inequities, increases vulnerability to disease, increases living costs, and impacts a household's ability to spend on education and nutrition. The movie Toilet- Ek Prem Katha problematizes the issue of open defecation. Conflicts between newlyweds escalate over the issue of open defecation leading to divorce. The movie raises serious concerns over prejudice of conservative people towards of the construction of toilet near their household. By exploring the issue of open defecation, the movie interconnects film and society envisaging a positive social change for hygienic atmosphere of the country. Moreover, the present research paper underlines the wider scope of the Film Studies, which encompasses almost all facets of the society and the need for the inclusion of this field in the curriculum.

Key Words: open defecation, issue, sanitation, movie, film studies, conflict, prejudice, society, etc.

Introduction:

Mahatma Gandhi rightly said that "Sanitation is more important than independence". The present research paper explores the issue of open defecation with a special reference to the movie entitled Toilet-Ek Prem Katha. The film was released on 11 August 2017. It is a romantic drama film starred by Akshay Kumar, Bhumi Pednekar, Anupam Kher, Sudhir Pandey and Divyendu Sharma and directed by Shree Narayan Singh. This satirical comedy highlights the issue of open defecation that persists in rural parts of the country. Keshav (Akshay Kumar) and Jaya (Bhumi Pednekar) love each other and decide to get married. Trouble begins when Jaya discovers that none of the houses in Keshav's village have a toilet. Upset with this unprogressive thinking, Jaya decides to leave Keshav and returns to her parents. A disheartened Keshav takes it upon himself to bring a change in his village and win back Jaya's love. Despite the initiation of Swatch Bharat Abhiyan (Clean India Drive) launched by government, open-defecation has become a serious issue. Along with food, cloth and shelter, adequate sanitization has become a basic human need. The lack of adequate sanitation exacerbates social inequities, increases vulnerability to disease, increases living costs, and impacts a household's ability to spend on education and nutrition. In fact, diseases caused by lack of hygiene and sanitation have a huge impact on people's health and financial resources. The issue of sanitation is particularly pressing for a country such as India, which still has the largest number of people defecating in the open. Adequate sanitation is critical for a country, which has expressed ambitious plans of economic growth and development, and yet continues to lag behind in terms of basic health and development indicators.

The Plot of the Movie:

After sufficient understanding of issue of open defecation, the present paper critically discusses it in context with the movie Toilet- Ek Prem Katha. The storyline of the movie shows that it is located in a small village Nandgaon of Uttar Pradesh state where women go to open fields and defecate behind the cover of bushes. Pandit Vimalnath Sharma, a superstitiously grappled priest gets his son Keshav married to a black buffalo, as it will bless the latter with prosperity. Simultaneously, Pandit also insists Keshav to get married only to a girl having two thumbs on her left hand. Keshav, being in love with Jaya, a rich girl of urban background, manages an artificial thumb on her left hand to which the unsuspecting father believes and agrees to their marriage. Conflict arises when Jaya discovers after her marriage to Keshav that she will defecate in the open field, as there is no toilet. In order to resolve her problem, Keshav makes some temporary arrangements such as taking her to neighbour's portable toilet or using toilets in trains at local station where train halts for seven minutes. However, at one time, the train departs before Jaya exists and in a fit of rage, she decides to stay with her parents threatening not to return if Keshav fails to build toilet. Keshav builds a toilet through travails which to his great distress, is demolished by the village Sarpanch and his father. Jaya files a divorce case in the court citing the primary reason of the unavailability of toilet, which grabs the media coverage, which hastens politicians and the concerned government departments to construct toilet at Keshav's house immediately. At this juncture, Keshav's mother sleeps on the doorstep and gets her hip broken and Pandit reluctantly enough helps his wife to use it. In the court hearing scene, the justice receives a letter from the chief minister's office requesting

not to grant divorce and Keshav's father comes to terms with Jaya's determination of having a nearby toilet by apologizing her for the suffering. The movie ends with a positive sign that the villagers line up to use mobile toilets outside their village while the construction of toilets throughout the village proceeds.

Critical Discussion:

The film is set against the backdrop of the worst sanitary condition of rural parts of the country. It explores the issue of open defecation, which results in spreading infectious diseases, contamination of water and air.

The film displays a 'conflict between tradition and modernity'. People residing in rural parts of the country are quite reluctant to make use of toilet. Rather they prepare to defecate in the open field, which indicates their traditional mindset and insincere attitude towards hygiene of their surroundings. The preoccupation of superstitious attitude towards the toilet building or using has created a major stumbling block in the development of sanitization in rural places. This is evident in the behaviour of Pandit Vimalnath Sharma, Keshav's father, who is the major opponent to Keshav as far as Keshav's attempts of toilet building near his house are concerned. His act of demolishing the toilet constructed by Keshav to bring his wife back is notoriously influenced by his prejudiced mindset. Contrary to traditional attitude of father-in-law, Jaya upholds the modern thinking, which necessitates the availability of toilet near household. Influenced by Jaya's determination, Keshav is intent on building a toilet because it is the only way out to him to win his love back. The film shows a transformation in the character of Keshav from a conservative youth to a progressive one who is committed to embark upon the toilet movement to make a defecation-free rural India. The film projects the struggle of a couple against the backward society.

'Self-determination for immediate change' is one of the significant elements, which can be observed in the characters of Keshav and Jaya. Jaya's threatening to Keshav about her demand for divorce indicates her independent thinking as well as her urge for the change. Keshav's efforts to build a toilet indicate his determined nature to stand against the odds of life.

Conclusion:

This film has a powerful social conscience. It showcases the failure of rural people to come to terms with government's initiatives regarding sanitization. The film is a satirical comedy in support of governmental campaigns to improve sanitation conditions in India, with an emphasis on the eradication of open defecation, especially in rural areas. The film highlights India's toilet problem, which is caused by their cultural and

religious sentiments. In Indian rural areas, people still do not have this necessity, which frustrates women, which further leads to sexual harassment. The end of the movie indicates a change in the attitude of rural people who line up for relieving themselves and the initiative taken on part of the government to build toilet in Nandgaon. Thus the film has handled one of the most controversial issues and necessitated to foreground such pressing issues through films with the view to raise awareness.

References:

1. Singh, Shree Narayan, director. *Toilet - Ek Prem Katha*, Reliance Entertainment, 11 Aug. 2017, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Toilet:_Ek_Prem_Katha. Accessed 5 July 2022.
2. Open Defecation: What Does It Take To Eradicate This? Where Does The World Stand In Progress? (n.d.). Retrieved July 5, 2022, from <https://theyf.org/open-defecation-what-does-it-take-to-eradicate-this-where-does-the-world-stand-in-progress/#:~:text=Open%20defecation%20is%20a%20human%20practice%20of%20defecating,trenches%20without%20any%20proper%20disposal%20of%20human%20excreta>.